

Migrolanding, the distribution of migrants as a solution to a reverse colonization problem

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Abstract. We define a new multi-objective optimization problem that consists in assigning migrants to different geographical subareas and, optionally, providing a job contract to them trying to maximize the satisfaction of the migrants and cover the labor needs of the different subareas. We provide an integer linear program for the problem and prove that the problem is NP-hard. We also point to potential sources of information to generate realistic instances for the problem.

Keywords: Immigration · migrant distribution · integer linear programming · combinatorial optimization

1 Introduction

In response to European expeditions, colonization, proselytization, and globalization there is an escape and a post-colonial migration from the Global South to the Global North. Post-colonial migratory movements are a response to the hospitality of the colonial era, without imperial ambition or forced proselytization but supported by the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Although the phenomenon of globalization is deconfiguring and tending towards decentralization that affects all countries, there is still a great imbalance of forces in the influence exercised by one over the other, by rich countries over poor ones. Giddens [2] speaks of “reverse colonization” when he refers to those non-Western countries that influence the West, although he maintains that colonization is a conception of the West alone. In this regard, we should mention concepts and ideas such as “inverse safaris” based on phenomena such as the so-called “black Mediterranean” or the Afrexit [1].

The reverse colonization can be the source for artistic works, and this is the goal of the Migrolanding project. But first, we need to simulate the moves of migrants. Thus, we consider a two-step process where first we solve an optimization problem related to migrant movement and then we use the solutions to create artistic works based on the moves. We face in this abstract the first part of the process and formulate the *migrant distribution problem* as a combinatorial optimization problem. We consider aspects like the spoken language and skills of the migrants (technological, linguistic, teaching, etc.) We also consider the presence of family and friends in the destination areas.

2 Problem Definition

In this section we present a mathematical formulation of the migrant distribution problem. In order to increase the level of abstraction, we will use the more general term “geographical area” instead of “continent” and the term “subarea” instead of “country”. This highlights the fact that the same formulation can be applied at very different geographical levels: continents, countries or smaller regions.

We have a set of n migrants that we denote with natural numbers: $M = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Each migrant i enters the geographical area using an entry point denoted by $e_i \in E$, where E is the set of all the entry points. We denote with $l_i \subseteq L$ the set of languages that i -th immigrant is fluent on and with $q_i \subseteq Q$ the subset of qualifications the immigrant has, where L is the set of all languages considered (English, Spanish, French, etc.) in the problem and Q the set of all the qualifications (technological, linguistic, teaching, etc.). We also consider the number of friends and family members the migrant already has in the geographical area and their subareas. We define a set of subareas $S = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ and we denote with c_{is} the number of contact persons the i -th migrant has in the s -th subarea.

The subarea offer jobs for migrants having a given qualification. We denote with t_{sq} the number of jobs that subarea $s \in S$ offers for migrants having qualification $q \in Q$. Each subarea defines a set of languages $A_s \subseteq L$ that are spoken in that subarea. Finally, there is a distance d_{es} between each entry point $e \in E$ and each subarea $s \in S$ that the migrant has to travel to go to the subarea. The presence of the migrant in a subarea has an initial cost f_s that depends on the subarea.

Now we can define the migrant distribution problem as a multi-objective optimization problem where we want to assign migrants to jobs and/or subareas such that the migrant satisfaction is maximized at the same time that jobs are covered and costs are minimized. We propose here an multi-objective integer linear programming formulation. Let x_{isq} be a 0-1 variable that takes value 1 when migrant i is assigned to a job requiring qualification q in subarea s and 0 otherwise. Let y_{is} be a 0-1 variable that takes value 1 when migrant i is assigned to subarea s . The problem is formally defined as follows:

$$\min \sum_{i \in M} \sum_{s \in S} d_{e_i s} y_{is} \quad (1)$$

$$\min \sum_{i \in M} \sum_{s \in S} f_s y_{is} \quad (2)$$

$$\max \sum_{i \in M} \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{q \in Q} x_{isq} \quad (3)$$

$$\max \sum_{i \in M} \sum_{s \in S} y_{is} [l_i \cap A_s \neq \emptyset] \quad (4)$$

$$\max \sum_{i \in M} \sum_{s \in S} y_{is} c_{is} \quad (5)$$

subject to:

$$x_{isj} \leq [j \in q_i] \quad \forall i \in M \quad \forall s \in S \quad \forall j \in Q \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{q \in Q} x_{isq} \leq 1 \quad \forall i \in M \quad (7)$$

$$x_{isq} \leq y_{is} \quad \forall i \in M \quad \forall s \in S \quad \forall q \in Q \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{s \in S} y_{is} = 1 \quad \forall i \in M \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{i \in M} x_{isq} \leq t_{sq} \quad \forall s \in S \quad \forall q \in Q \quad (10)$$

$$x_{isq}, y_{is} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in M \quad \forall s \in S \quad \forall q \in Q \quad (11)$$

In Equations (4) and (6) we use the Iverson bracket which is 1 when the Boolean condition inside is true and 0 otherwise. Equation (1) minimizes the distance from the entry point of the migrants to their assigned subarea, while Equation (2) minimizes the initial cost associated to the migrant in the subarea. Equations (3), (4) and (5) maximize the number of migrants with jobs assigned, the number of migrants in a subarea speaking a language in which he or she is fluent and the number of contacts in the subarea assigned to the migrants.

Regarding the constraints, Equations (6) prevent migrants to be assigned jobs for which they are not qualified and Equations (7) prevent migrants to be assigned two or more jobs. If a migrant is assigned a job in a subarea, then he or she must be assigned to the subarea (Equations (8)). Observe, however, that a migrant can be assigned a subarea without a job in that subarea. In fact, Equations (9) force each migrant to be assigned a country. The number of migrants assigned to jobs in a subarea cannot exceed the number of positions (Equations (10)). Finally, Equations (11) set the domain for the decision variables.

3 Potential algorithms and instances

It is not difficult to prove that the problem is NP-hard by a reduction of the knapsack problem to the migrant distribution problem. Let us assume we are given a knapsack instance of size n (number of objects) where the value and weights of the objects are given by v_i and w_i , respectively, for $1 \leq i \leq n$. We build an instance of the migrant distribution problem where there are n subareas and n migrants. There is only one qualification that all migrants have and one language all of them speak and that is spoken in all the subareas. We set only one job per subarea and the initial cost of per migrant in the subareas is 0. We set the distances and number of contacts in the subareas as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} d_{e_{is}} &= w_i \delta_i^s, \\ c_{is} &= v_i \delta_i^s, \end{aligned}$$

where $\delta_i^s = [i = s]$ is the Kronecker delta. Then, finding the Pareto front of this instance solves the given Knapsack instance.

Regarding the instances we can generate realistic instances of the problem focused on Europe. Frontex provides statistics about the migrants by entry point. Figure 1 shows in a map the number of migrants entering Europe in the years 2021 and 2022. We can observe that the numbers are around the hundred of thousands. That means that exact solvers, like integer linear programming solvers are probably not able to explore the Pareto optimal set and we need to use heuristic algorithms like evolutionary algorithms and other metaheuristics.

Fig. 1. Number of illegal border-crossings in Jan-Dec 2021/2022. Source: Frontex-<https://www.frontex.europa.eu>.

4 Conclusions

In this abstract we define the migrant distribution problem, a new multi-objective optimization problem that models a real-world problem related to immigration. The use of a multi-objective formulation allows the decision-makers (politicians) to consider different aspects in the decision. Future work should create a benchmarks of instances of the problem and should use state-of-the-art optimization techniques to solve them. We will also advance to step two of the migrolanding project: creating artistic visualizations based on the migrant moves generated by the solutions to the optimization problem.

References

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